

PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF THE JADIDS AND REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF NATIONAL EDUCATION.

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Abstract. This article provides an overview of the life path of the Jadid enlighteners, the history and main ideas of Jadidism, the pedagogical views of the Jadids today and their dedication to this path, as well as opinions on how new views emerged at that time and what ideas were put forward in them.

Keywords: New, new method, school, education, upbringing, reform, madrasa. Turkish language, development, literacy, ancestors, generation, perfection

It is natural to ask questions about how Jadidism appeared, what was the main idea behind its emergence. We can find answers to these questions by first knowing the history of Jadidism. Jadidism or Jadidism (Arabic: jadīd - new) - late 19th century, early 20th century, a socio-political, educational movement that became important in the life of Turkestan, Caucasus, Crimea, and Tatarstan. came into being. It spread in Central Asia from the 90s of the 19th century. The representatives of this movement called for the fight for development, the development of Turkic languages, the enrichment of literature in these languages, the study of secular sciences, the use of scientific achievements, and the fight for the equality of women and men. Enlightenment leaders set the main goal of developing the education system, making the population literate, and through this, developing the country.

The main ideas and goals of Jadidism were:

- Freeing Turkestan from medieval backwardness and religious superstition, Sharia reform
- spreading enlightenment to the people
- Struggle to establish an autonomous government in Turkestan

To build a free and prosperous society by establishing a constitutional monarchy and parliament in Bukhara and Khiva, and then to a democratic republic, to introduce a stable national currency and to form a national army. Literacy of the growing young generation was one of the main goals. Cultural and educational centers opened by some groups of free-thinking and progressive people in Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara, Samarkand and Khiva. The Jadidist movement was formed from the societies and associations of the direction. The word "Jadid" means new. Bringing innovation to the education system, organizing lessons in a new way, and making the young generation literate has become an urgent issue. In the early 20th century, the progressive leaders of the Jadidism movement - Behbudi, Fitrat, Cholpon, Munavvar Qori, Abdulla Avloniy - became stronger in their creativity and activity. Jadids put forward the idea of unifying the peoples of Turkestan and fighting for the national independence of the whole country. As Mahmudhoja Behbudi noted, "In each country, the initiative to reform and culture tools and the movement to take initiative began to appear on the part of the country's youth, so our In Turkestan as well, the

school, which is at the door of culture, is the herald of renaissance and reform, the national press, the movement of enthusiastic young people, was created in the shadow of the guardians of education. Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov spoke about the responsibility of the parents in the education and upbringing of the child, and said that there are those who try their best to make their child enlightened. noted. Jadids emphasized that parents are involved in the education of their children and prepare them for schools and madrasas. After studying in schools and madrasas, they said that young people should improve their knowledge in educational institutions of developed countries and acquire modern sciences. Of course, not everyone accepted these ideas positively.

As a result, very few children became literate. Up to now, the study of the creative heritage of the modern enlighteners, the analysis and use of the works written by them is being carried out on a large scale. expressed such thoughts about the difficult path during the period "... In the next six years, the number of pre-school educational organizations in our republic increased almost 6 times, from 4988 to 29420, and the number of higher educational institutions increased from 77 to 213. New types of presidential schools, creativity schools, and specialized schools are being established in our country. The intelligence, will and tenacity of our progressive ancestors serve as a model school for all of us in raising our children to be well-rounded people who are loyal to national and universal values. We consider it an urgent task to further study the activities of modern scientists in cooperation with international scientific centers and world scientists. Through this unique heritage, we can find correct answers to many questions that concern humanity today. The more we actively promote this priceless wealth, the more our people, especially our youth, will realize the value of today's peaceful and free life. I wish all the participants of the conference good health, new creative achievements, and success in the work of the conference." (From his greeting to the participants of the international conference dedicated to the study of the heritage of the ancients. March 6, 2023). Abdulla Awlani is a shining example of modern enlighteners. The main goal of the writer was to introduce the children, who are the future of the nation, to the history of Islam, even if only briefly, from the elementary school, to increase their religious knowledge, and to instill the light of faith in their hearts. Abdulla Awlani's works are commendable. Along with the culture and enlightenment of the Uzbek people, it was considered important in the socio-political life of the neighboring Afghan people in 1919-1920. In his time, he served as the political representative and consul of the Soviet government in Afghanistan. In addition to writing works, Abdulla Avloni is engaged in opening schools, making the people literate, educating Uzbek women and girls, training teachers and intellectuals. In 1923-24, he was the head of the women's and men's educational institutions in the old city, in 1924-29 he was a teacher at the Tashkent military school, in 1925-34 at the Central Asian Communist University, Central Asian Agricultural School, He teaches at the State University of Central Asia. He worked as a professor and head of the Department of Language and Literature of the Faculty of Pedagogy. In 1933, he compiled and published "Literary Christology" for the 7th grade of Uzbek schools. Abdulla Avloni is critical with the nicknames "Hijran", "Nabil", "Indamas", "Shuhrat", "Tangriquli", "Surayo", "Shapaloq", "Chol", "Ab", "Chigaboy", "Abdulhaq". and a scientific article, more than 4000 lines of poetry did Avloni was awarded the title of "Hero of Labor" in 1927. In 1930, he was awarded the honorary title of "Zarbdari of Public Education of Uzbekistan". Currently, there are a number of schools named after Abdulla Avloni in our independent Uzbekistan. The above-mentioned modern enlighteners risked their lives for their country, people, and their spiritual development. Because

with the language of the nation, with its spiritual perfection, with the understanding and knowledge of the mind, it can achieve high goals.

In conclusion, the literacy level of young people has increased significantly due to the hard work of modern enlighteners. Various works written in our national mother tongue have not lost their importance and value to this day. The introduction of a new education system, the promotion of studying in new conditions and in a new way, as a result of this, has set itself the goal of increasing the level of knowledge of the people, and it has achieved this goal to a significant extent. In developed countries, they have introduced a system of free education for young people who are hungry for knowledge, thus they have started development in the country. Nowadays, special attention is paid to learning the experience of modern enlighteners, because for the development of the country, it is the task of today's teacher to educate and educate young people who are passionate and patriotic in accordance with our ancestors. is considered After all, Abdulla Awlani said, "To lose the national language is to lose the soul of the nation." If we, the future teachers, can apply the rich heritage of the modern enlighteners of our ancestors to the growing young generation, the spiritual maturity of our generations will undoubtedly be higher and will be perfect.

REFERENCES

1. SH. Mirziyoyev: Jadidlar merosini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan xalqarokonferensiya ishtirokchilariga yo'llagan tabrigidan.2023 yil 6-mart
2. Oblomurodov N, Hazratqulov A va boshqalar. O'zbekiston tarixi.(o'quv qo'llanma)T.2011
3. Behbudiy M. Muhtaram yoshlarga murojaat. Oyna-1914. 41-bet
4. M.Abdurashidxonov. Xotiralarimdan(Jadidchilik tarixidan lavhalar). Sharq 2001. 108-109-betlar
5. F.F Raximova.“Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda deontologik kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning pedagogik mazmuni” xalqaro ilmiy nazariy konferensiya materiallari. Buxoro-2024,176-177 betlar.
6. F.F Raximova. “Ta'limda innovatsion jarayonlar hamda bo'lajak o'qituvchilar faoliyatida innovatsiya va uning samaradorligi”. Pedagogik mahorat,Buxoro-2024.N:4